

SYMBOLIC MEANINGS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF PATTERNS AND DECORATIONS IN CENTRAL ASIAN ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS IN THE XIV-XV CENTURIES

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the origin of patterns and ornaments used in the historical monuments of Central Asia, their division into species and their differences from each other, scientifically analyzes the patterns and ornaments and provides information about their compositional solutions.

In Central Asia, there are three main groups of architectural ornaments: girih Islamic and written (khushhat). The girih group of ornaments (derived from the Arabic word girih "knot") includes patterns formed by the repetition of a knot of intricate hand-shaped shapes, based on square, triangular, rectangular, and circular divisions (repeating parts). Distributions (also called 'rapport') can also be repeated at the entrance in a straight and left-right position, i.e. right and right and vice versa. Since girihs are based on handicrafts, they are also called handicrafts in the literature. In terms of structure, nodes are divided into types consisting of straight lines, curved lines and mixed lines.

The patterns in the Islamic group, on the

other hand, are sharply different from the girihs and are composed of repetitive distributions in a plant-like form. The basis of the Islamic pattern is the bushes, bushes, leaves and trunks. That is why Islamic is a type of plant-like pattern. Tanob is a core drawing that forms the basis of a plant-like pattern. According to the composition of Islamic patterns can be divided into ruta, munabbat, madoxil, orange, chain. The display is an intricate and complete Islamic pattern composition surrounded by a border pattern. It is mainly used to decorate the interiors of Central Asian architectural monuments. It is also possible that the Islamic pattern is mixed with girih in the composition of the show. In this, the girih always plays the role of the main and

the Islamic one complements the pattern, and the Islamic never crosses the girih.

The composition can be processed even if it is pure from the entrance. They are also composed of basic and complementary patterns, such as the Islamic representation. In this case, first the main large girih is developed, and then a small filler girder is drawn into it. The ruta is a two-way patterned partition and is mainly used for the frame. In this case, the base of the pattern consists of a square or a rectangle, and the composition of the

pattern consists of a uniformly repeating distribution on all four sides. Munabbat is used to decorate large surfaces. Madoxil is a left-right recurring tulip-like Islamic pattern type. It is diverse in appearance and consists of buds, tulips, flowers, three leaves and other shapes. Orange is an oval or circle-shaped Islamic pattern composition. The chain is a framed pattern formed by the continuous repetition of the shapes of a triangular pyramid (Figure 1).

Figure 1. There are three main groups of architectural ornaments in Central Asia: A-girih, B-Islamic V-written (epigraphic)

The written (calligraphic) group of ornaments includes epigraphic patterns used in architecture as ornaments on the exterior and interior of buildings. Such patterns have been common in Central Asian architecture since the tenth to eleventh centuries. Written ornaments are usually made on separate books on the roof of the building, on the round fences of the domes, on the doorposts at the entrance to the buildings, and inside the building on the altar, columns, tombstones, ceilings and doors. The inscriptions are written in the Arabic alphabet (mainly in Kufic, Suls, Naskh scripts) and are devoted to religious, philosophical and educational topics in terms of meaning. The names of the

sponsors of the buildings and the dates of construction are also written on them. From the system of Arabic letters, meaningful sentences, serjilo, elegant compositions are created.

Written ornaments are more common in religious and enlightenment monuments: mosques, madrasas, mausoleums and khanaqahs. The composition of the inscriptions depended on the structure and dimensions of the main architectural forms. For example, on the surface of large flanges in the shape of a circle, the inscription is formed on the visible part of it, forming a circular row, that is, a large ring. Architectural inscriptions can also be processed into several rows of different

thicknesses. The inscriptions on the square-shaped surfaces are in a monolithic composition, often carved in a single row. To fill the square surface, the letters "alif", "lom", "zol", "dol" were written aloud. In particular, the books on the doors of the mausoleum of Qusam ibn Abbas in the ensemble of Shahi Zinda and the mausoleum of Khoja Ahmad Yassavi have such decorations.

In addition to epigraphic ornaments, we

also find zoomorphic tiles in Central Asian architecture. They are mostly found on the canopies of building roofs. On the roofs of the Anau Mosque in Turkmenistan, the Sherdor and Nodir-Devonbegi (17th century) madrasas in Samarkand, and the Nadir-Devonbegi and Abdulazizkhan madrasas in Bukhara (17th century), we see images of legendary animals, semurg birds, deer or lions and owls (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Patterns on the roofs of Sherdor and Nodir-Devonbegi madrasas in Samarkand

Architectural exterior decorations are mainly brick, made of vinegar tiles or rivets, as well as patterns carved in stone, while interior decorations can be made of tile, ganch or wood, ganch, stone, wood carving or painting, as well as painting on wall plaster, depending on the material. Depending on these features, architectural ornaments can be divided into several separate types, namely brick, tile, plaster and wood carvings, wall paintings, stone carvings, muqarnas and kundal ornaments. Because these patterns are widely used in architecture, they have been preserved in Central Asia from ancient times to the present day and are widespread in practice.

Islam (VII century), which entered Central Asia as a result of the Arab conquest, forbade the depiction of living beings in

murals.

However, the pursuit of beauty was one of the peculiar spiritual features of the development of society, and the prohibition of the fine arts led to the development of new ways in this art. For the same reason, in Muslim architecture or in Central Asia, ornamental girih and Islamic patterns began to replace the magnificent murals with Islamic themes. At the same time, Islam is adapting this direction to its own interests. Along with handasavi girih and Islamic patterns in architectural decorations, the verses and hadiths of the Qur'an are becoming obscure patterns in Arabic suls and nax inscriptions. Skilled tile painters begin to transfer rare specimens of calligraphy to the walls of architectural monuments. Thus, in architectural embroidery, a monumental ornamental

and graceful (written) direction emerges instead of a thematic majestic mural color fine art.

It is known that in Islam there was no resistance to images and statues at first. That is why the Qur'an does not forbid the depiction of living beings or the making of statues. Some caliphs who used it in the IX-X centuries decorated their palaces with attractive colorful murals and statues. However, later, in the late tenth and twelfth centuries, when the hadiths and the Shari'ah came into full force in Islam, Islam was opposed to the worshipful and clear depiction of any creatures and statues. Because it was understood as a broad path to paganism against Islam. This creed was later formed in the hadiths to the point where it completely forbade the depiction of living beings in general, and in such depictions lies the imitation of Allah's creation, and therefore it is explained as a sin to draw them. However, these beliefs have been interpreted and emphasized differently in different sects and at different times. For example, during the Phytomids in Egypt (tenth century) the observance of Islamic beliefs in the field of fine arts was not fully formed. During this period, there were even separate halls in Cairo displaying portraits of caliphs and poets. But images of open romance and obscenity were strongly condemned even in those days.

The first is that the processed image is created in a worshipful, i.e., pagan, and convenient way (e.g., in the form of a clear statue); the second is the tendency of the image to arouse inward, i.e. spiritual, especially greedy feelings in a person (which is very inconvenient for a Muslim and tends to involuntarily disrupt his order of ablution). Of course, in both cases, the

degree to which the image was clearly or abstractly processed was also important. Based on these key factors and the ideas associated with them, the Shariah has addressed the issue of what is forbidden or not to Muslims in the image.

As a result, as mentioned above, in architecture, monumental patterns with murals are replaced by ornamental ornaments: girih, Islamic and written (calligraphic or epigraphic) patterns, and they become the main type of patterns.

Flowers in the Islamic pattern: the rose is a symbol of peace, longevity, the wavy flower stalk is a symbol of wealth and prosperity, the twigs and leaves are a symbol of youth and rejuvenation, white is a symbol of happiness and luck, blue is a symbol of high faith, red is a symbol of joy and youth.

The demand for fine arts in Islam is that it emphasizes the image symbol, which not only evokes emotions, but also discovers harmony and harmony. That is why the harmony of form, content and patterns in Islam is a consequence of vital needs.

By the VIII-XIII centuries, the art of decorating the style of buildings with brick patterns in Central Asian architecture rose to a high level. The very elegant and diverse brick patterns of the Samanid mausoleum in Bukhara are proof of our opinion. Among the architectural monuments of the XI-XII centuries, the interiors, walls, roofs, arches of the mausoleums in Uzgen (Osh region), conditionally called North, Middle, South, are distinguished by very elegant plaster, wood and colored patterns.

In the XIV-XV centuries in Central Asian architecture several new directions of fine arts and painting appeared. During this period, the experiences gained before the period of the previous Mongol conquest

(girih, islimi, madoxil, gulguncha ornaments) are further developed. New types of exterior architectural decorations in Movarounahr are used: glazed clay carvings (reznaya polivnaya terracotta), glazed colored cross-section tiles (mosaics), monochromatic colored ceramic patterns - rivets (majolica). Parchin is a glazed solid ceramic board. Drawings on its surface are decorated with different colors and given a secret. An ornamental ceramic board made in this style is called majolica. Unlike tile tiles, the surface is only painted and glazed to the same color. Exterior architectural ornaments of the XIV-XV centuries are reflected in various Islamic, girih or "madoxil" and "Devonian" style, indoor vinegar ornaments are mainly in lavuvad (purple) and turquoise, and calligraphy is in "suls". Such colorful compositions were widely used in Samarkand in the mausoleums of Shodimulk, Amir Hussein, Amirzoda, Shirinbeka aqa in Shahizinda.

From the 14th century onwards, Islamic floral patterns began to occupy a leading position in interior decoration in architecture according to girih ornaments. Girih, on the other hand, was mostly used in the decoration of large-scale walls and towers, along with Arabic inscriptions on exterior decorations. Colors of Islamic patterns: carved mysterious ceramic ornaments, flat tile patterns with a single layer, Arabic letters that are clearly embossed on the level of entwined attractive leafy petals, silent mountains decorated with glazed small carved flowers, floral "embroidered" applied. Blue, purple and white colors were widely used in the entrance patterns. The carved mysterious Islamic ceramic ornaments are made in two colors: purple or purple and

white. Flat Islamic tile ornaments were adorned in two to seven different colors (blue, white, purple, black, yellow, orange, and in some cases gold).

By this time the architectural epigraphic Arabic calligraphy was also further refined. They are embroidered with large Kufic inscriptions on the level of the flanges that support the sky-blue domes so that they can be read from a distance. Leaving a special place for inscriptions even on the level of the roofs, they are processed in large Arabic luxurious "suls" and straight-line multi-line "naskh" calligraphy. The height of the inscription on the roof of Timur's Mosque in Samarkand was about one and a half meters, which, according to Babur, could be read from a distance of 2.5 kilometers.

By the 14th and 15th centuries, the use of muqarnas, a type of star-shaped ornament designed to decorate the inside of domes, was widespread in Central Asian and Eastern architecture. It is now widely used not only for interior decoration, but also on the arches of external roofs. The mausoleum of Gori Amir in Samarkand, the mausoleum of Shodimulk in Shahizinda, and the Samarkand madrasah of Ulugbek are unique examples of muqarnas.

In the second half of the 15th century, the "kundal" style of embroidery emerged. In this style, the colors are painted on white ganch or clay that takes on the color of a local red lump. The embossed decoration on the basis of the red box is decorated with colorful Islamic patterns, creating a wonderful type of decoration. Blue, light green, red, and white are followed by blue and green. Or a little simpler kundal patterns are made on a white or blue base with gold water running and thin Islamic ornaments.

During this period, the monumental murals, which had flourished in Central Asia since ancient times, were revived. They reflected images of living things: humans and animals, as well as nature and catastrophes. Large murals (monumental fine art) dedicated to specific life themes were displayed in his gardens during the reign of Amir Temur. Pictures of nature and astronomy, seven climates and planets were depicted on the walls of the observatory, which he built during the reign of Ulugbek. In the gardens and palaces there was a collection of paintings on the theme of life. Porcelain patterns imported from China during the reign of Ulugbek were also one of the innovations in this field.

Unfortunately, the unique murals, which flourished in the 14th and 15th centuries, mainly in Samarkand and Herat, have not survived. This type of fine art did not develop in the country in the following periods. Only in our time this direction has developed and found its new theme. In other words, the miniature art of the Oriental style was revived on the basis of the national spirit and ancient traditions, and became widespread not only in the pages of books, but also in the form of monumental color murals, gaining an attractive national direction. In our opinion, the next step is not to loosen this line, but to maintain nationality by introducing various secular styles and innovations into it.

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